

Assessing The Impact
Of Household Food
Waste On The Ghanaian
Economy From Selected
Communities In Accra
Metropolitan Area

Sonny Gad Attipoe

*Masters Student, China Agriculture University
Beijing, College of Food Science and Nutritional
Engineering. No. 17 Qinghua Donglu, Haidian
District, Beijing 100083, P.R China*

Prof. Li ZaiGui

*Lecturer, China Agriculture University Beijing,
College of Food Science and Nutritional Engineering,
No. 17 Qinghua Donglu, Haidian District, Beijing
100083, P.R China*

ABSTRACT

Every human in Ghana has a fundamental right to be free from hunger and the right to adequate food, this right to adequate food is realized only when every man, woman and child has the physical and economic access at all times to adequate, healthy and nutritious food. Unfortunately, when this is fulfilled, consumers turn to waste food at the household level via methods that could be avoided to enhance food security. This present study examines the extent to which 120 households selected from 12 residential areas in Accra Metropolitan Area contributes to household food waste. Specifically, the socio-economic class that generates the highest waste, percentage composition of waste fraction and per capital generation rate was determined. Results show that average household food waste generation rate was 0.12 kg/person/day, with high income class areas recording the highest generation rate of 0.2 kg/person/day, middle and low income class areas recording 0.1 kg/person/day and 0.06 kg/person/day respectively. Total waste analyzed was 1813.30 kg; high-income areas with high economic activity recorded the highest food waste of 920.10 kg as compared to 369.30 kg, low-income areas and 523.90 kg, middle-income areas. Dairy products with percentage fractional wastage of 28% were recorded as the highest food wasted among all three socio-economic classes.

Keywords: Household food waste, Generation rate, Food security, Ghana-Accra

1. INTRODUCTION

Food waste is an enormous issue in Ghana, but just how enormous? Worldwide, we throw away almost one third of the food produced for human consumption (FAO, 2013). Food waste by definition refers to food that is intended for human consumption is not used as such ((*Soethoudt and Bos-Brouwers, 2014*). Absence of quantitative data in Ghana on the annual types of food and drink wasted, why it is thrown away, and where the material goes to is the only obstacle in this research. It is inevitable to totally reduce the world's food waste to zero but advocacy and relief programmes are currently trying to significantly reduce the amount of food wasted annually not only at the household level but within the food supply chain. Ghana in 2013 imported over 45% food commodities amounting over \$ 1.5 billion to compliment local production and demand (MOFA, 2013), of which the country lost \$ 8.9 billion to both avoidable and unavoidable food wastage with the highest occurring with the distribution and consumer level of our food supply chain. With population estimate of 24.4 million, Ghana cannot afford to lose its food to the landfills hence appropriate measures must be taken to curb the household food waste.

It is estimated that 4.2 million tones of food and drink waste is generated each year in the UK, worth about 12.5 billion pounds (Quested et al., 2012). The report further makes it clear that food waste in the home is not the only source of food waste but it makes the single largest contribution; around 50% across all sectors in the UK. But this is not just a problem in the UK, it's a worldwide problem.

In 2012, the total amount of food waste in the Netherlands was between 1.7 and 2.6 billion kilos (*Soethoudt and Bos-Brouwers, 2014*). This is the total amount wasted in the food supply chain, from the farm via the shop or food service to the consumer. With respect to total wasted kilocalories, European consumers at home are the biggest wasters with a share of 38%. This is followed by agriculture (23%), the hotel and catering sector (14%), the processing and storage sector (12%), supermarkets (9%) and the food industry (5%) (*Lipinski et al., 2013*).

The United States is not an exception because according to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, more than 64 billion pounds of food is thrown away each year, making food waste the single largest component of municipal solid waste reaching landfills and incinerators. A large portion is from household waste, the food and drink that we buy but don't consume. The amount of food disposed by individuals varies significantly, with waste increasing as disposable incomes rise. For individuals tossing food is money down the drain. Bloom (2010) estimated that the average American household throws out up to US\$2,200 a year. This wasted food finds way into landfills, creating the greenhouse gas methane and other heterogeneous gases which is a significant concern for society. Economic concern is that this doesn't account for the wasted energy, water, labor, and other inputs that go into growing, processing, and transporting food from farm houses to consumers. While reducing consumer-generated waste is unlikely to increase the availability of food for the needy, many experts contend it is irresponsible to waste so much food when so many people are struggling to find enough to eat.

It is urgent to help Ghanaian consumers cut down on household food waste, although is not easy given entrenched habits and norms, but it is possible. A significant contribution and awareness from food retailers and producers is increasingly looking at ways to help individuals minimize household food waste, use food that is still wholesome, and finally, encouraging composting of food that won't be consumed. Food security and food sovereignty isn't just about producing more food to feed the estimated 24.4 million Ghanaians; it is about trying to reduce the amount of food we waste.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The main objectives of this study is to determine the socio economic class in selected parts of Accra that contributes to wasting the most amount of household food, reasons why such waste happens at their home, types of foods wasted the most, effects on the environment and economic impacts of such waste generated. Finally, participating households will be supported with knowledge in creating and keeping food waste diaries and how to suppress factors that causes food waste.

3. DATA AND METHODS

A survey source sorting and separation was conducted using 120 households selected from different communities within the Accra Metropolitan Area, (AMA) of Ghana from May to July 2016 for data collection on waste composition, reasons behind their generation and the economic impact of household waste generated.

3.1 STUDY AREA

Ghana is located in West Africa and has a total land area of 238,533 square kilometers. Administratively Ghana is segregated into 10 regions with their regional capitals (Fig. 1), which are divided into Metropolitan, Municipal and District Assemblies (MMDAs). Ghana has 216 MMDAs: 6 Metropolitan areas (Cape Coast, Tamale, Kumasi, Tema, Accra, Secondi-Takoradi), 49 Municipalities and 161 Districts (Ghana Statistical Service, 2012). With 16 MMDAs classification, Accra is the Metropolitan and regional capital of the Greater Accra Region and Ghana (Fig. 1). With an estimated population of 1,848,614, Accra is located at 5.56 latitude, -0.20 longitude and is situated at elevation of 61 meters above sea level with city coordinates 5°33'00" N 0°12' 00" W'.

Figure 1: Map of Ghana showing 10 Regional Capitals

Source: Perry-Castaneda Library Map Collection

The city of Accra covers a total land area of 173km² and is bounded to the North by Ga West Municipal, the West by Ga South Municipal, the South by Gulf of Guinea, and the East by La Dadekotopon Municipal (Ghana Statistical Service, 2012). The Accra Metropolitan Assembly currently has 10 sub metropolitan district councils consisting of 72 communities (Fig. 2). The Private informal sector is the main avenue for employment followed by the private formal sector, and finally the public /Government sector. This research was conducted using 120 households in 12 selected communities within the Accra Metropolitan Area. Due to simplicity and easy of data collection, the selected communities and households were classified into three categories as summarize here:

Fig 2: Demographic and housing aggregate poverty pockets of Accra Area

Source: Global Communications Ghana

3.1.1 HIGH INCOME CLASS AREA

These are mainly residential areas characterized by good roads, with social amenities and services such as water, electricity, community security, supermarkets, good drainage systems, hospitals, community international schools, and well planned houses. The houses in these areas are often single or story building with paved or grassed compounds. Majority of the residents in these areas are expatriates working for major companies in Ghana. The houses are mostly occupied by single or small family size. Although it is perceived that those in this class are high incomes earners based on their elegant life style, the study did not actually focus on the income stratification of the household but rather focused on what is on their shopping list.

3.1.2 MIDDLE INCOME CLASS AREA

These are residential areas characterized by flats and bungalows and fenced in some instances. The buildings are mostly semi-detached in the estates and detached when privately owned. They have fenced compounds with backyard gardens and cheap landscaping. The buildings are mostly occupied by more than one household. They may have some level of improved amenities such as good roads, electricity and water.

3.1.3 LOW INCOME CLASS AREA

These are areas located in slums with poor social services and amenities. Their buildings are mostly single rooms with poor ventilation. Lack of basic and social amenities like good roads, hospitals, supermarkets, proper drainage, international schools and security is the prime concern. Compound houses are source of classification for this type of settlement where more than 5 people sleep in crowded single room. Diseases like malaria, cholera and HIV are very common in majority of these areas.

3.2 SOURCES AND METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected from 120 households selected from 12 communities each in High income class area (East legon, Airport residential, Dzorwulu, and Tesano), Middle income class area (Dansoman, Bubushie, Mataheko

and Osu) and Low income class area (Nima, Newtown, Sukura and Chorkor). Households in the mentioned communities were visited to inform them about the survey and to receive feedback on their willingness to participate in the study. Students were used to administer questionnaires to participating household which solicited information from shopping list items to waste generated in the fridge, kitchen and how they end up in waste bins. Finally, participating households were educated on how to accurately complete the household food diaries administered.

3.2.1 SORTING PROCEDURE

Initial sorting was done by members of the household and further checking was done by research team. Plastic bins with sealed covers were used to collect food waste generated by participating households. Collection, separation and sorting were done on weekly basis for total duration of 4 weeks per household. The sorters and supervisors were trained on all aspects of sorting, measurements and data recording using excel sheets. The number of sorters per household was ratio 1 sorter to 5 households. Thus a total of 32 trained sorters were used in all 120 households in 12 selected communities. Protective clothing was given to all personnel involved in the study.

3.2.2 WEIGHING OF SORTED WASTE

The sorted waste was collected and weighed using a lab spring balance (50-100kg) and a top pan balance of various capacities: 2kg, 5 kg, and 10 kg. The waste collected was further segregated into 11 various organic fractions at the household level. These Include:

- Bread
- Dairy products
- Vegetables
- Fruits
- Tubers- yam, plantain, cocoyam and potatoes
- Meat
- Cakes and biscuits
- Beverages
- Leftovers
- Rice and pasta
- Sauces and Fats

The percentage composition of each household food waste component was calculated by the formula

$$\text{Percentage composition of waste fraction} = \frac{\text{Weight of separated food waste}}{\text{The total mixed weight sampled}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

To determine the per capita generation rate of each household, we counted on the weekly waste data results per the number of household generating the waste by the formula

Per capita household food waste generation

$$= \frac{\text{Weight of household food waste generated}}{\text{Total number of persons in household} \times \text{Total number of generation days}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 TOTAL WASTE GENERATION

A total household food waste load of 1813.30 kg was weighed, out of which 369.30 kg belongs to low socioeconomic status, 523.90 kg to the middle status, and 920.10 kg to the high status. (Figure 1) below provides details of the total household food waste analyzed for the three socio economic class over four weeks sampling period.

Fig 1: Total household food waste analyzed

Source: Researcher's field data (2016)

As shown above, the high income class areas generated the highest amount of total waste analyzed, studies conducted by researchers in other countries supports this argument. Reports by Williams (1998) indicates that household waste sizes vary according to changes in consumer patterns and economic growth rates and depends on standard of living, season of the year, day of the week, population habits and the geographical site of settlement. The total population for the high class income areas generating the most amount of waste was below the two other socioeconomic classes (Table 1). As indicated previously, this class is characterized by high standards of living, high purchasing power and busy working lifestyle which lure them into thinking filling their shopping baskets and refrigerators at home is the best way out. Unfortunately, days pass and they don't consume all what they bought leaving it to find its way into the landfills.

Table 1: Generation of household food waste in three socioeconomic classes in Accra

Residential Status	Specific Study Area	Population in area	Total waste Analyzed/kg	Total households surveyed	Total people generating the waste	Sampling duration/ weeks
High Class Income Area	East Legon	3,742	220.70	10	40	4
	Airport Residential	2,591	232.80	10	44	4

	Dzorwulu	3,595	235.70	10	39	4
	Tesano	3,032	230.90	10	44	4
Middle Class Income Area	Dansoman	4,791	170.70	10	39	4
	Bubuashi	3,342	127.50	10	42	4
	Mataheko	3,454	109.30	10	47	4
	Osu	3,078	116.40	10	51	4
Low Class Income Area	Nima	5,089	97.40	10	37	4
	Newtown	4,989	92.30	10	57	4
	Sukura	3,789	98.40	10	53	4
	Chorkor	5,982	81.20	10	50	4

Source; Researcher's field data (2016)

4.2 WASTE GENERATION RATE

On the average, rate of household food waste generation was 0.12 kg/person/day for all 120 households in the 3 socioeconomic classes. The high income class areas recorded the highest food waste generation rate of 0.2 kg/person/day whilst the middle and low income class areas recorded 0.1 kg/person/day and 0.06 kg/person/day respectively. The much lower generation rate in low class income areas could be attributed to the low economic activities as compared to the other classes.

Fig 2; Household food waste generation rate.

Source; Researcher's field data (2016)

It is important to note that quantitative data on household food waste generation rate is currently unavailable in Ghana, hence majority of researchers rely heavily on qualitative data and municipal solid waste generation data. It's not bad to emphasize here, in this research paper that majority of researchers with interest in waste generation and management are particularly concerned about how total waste generated from a particular community affects the environment and its economic implications on the country. Household food generation rate data obtained in this present study was significantly lower than that obtained by researchers in Ghana. The explanation to this wide variation was due to the fact that they concentrated on municipal solid waste and household waste generation rate whilst this paper only concentrates on household food waste which is just a smaller fraction of municipal solid waste. Waste generation rate across Ghana irrespective of the socioeconomic considerations ranged from 0.2 to 0.8 kg/person/day Miezah et al. (2015), this is also the range for most of the

cities in sub-saharan Africa (Friedrich and Trois, 2011; UNEP, 2013). However, higher generation rates have been reported for OECD countries, 1.39 kg/person/day (OECD, 2010). Similar findings by Miezah et al. (2015) on municipal solid waste in selected regions in Ghana, proposes the fact that, high socioeconomic class areas generated the highest quantity of waste in the study areas; 0.56 kg/person/day followed by the middle class areas, 0.49 kg/person/day and the low class areas 0.47 kg/person/day for the regional capitals. Different schools of thoughts regarding waste generation differences among socioeconomic areas where the higher socioeconomic classes generated higher waste have been reported by Asase (2011) as; 0.63 kg/person/day for Asokwa a high class area, 0.52 kg/person/day for Atonsu, a Middle class area and 0.27 kg/person/day for Ahinsan, a low class socioeconomic area all in the Kumasi metropolis. Studies by Owusu-Ansah (2008) obtained similar generation rates data among the different socioeconomic class areas in Greater Accra Region.

4.3 FRACTIONS OF HOUSEHOLD WASTE

The impact of seasonal variation on generation and composition of household food waste was not considered since this is believed to have no significant impact on it. This is supported by studies conducted in Kumasi (Ashanti Region of Ghana) by Ketibuah et al. (2004), Kotoka (2001), Opoku (1999) within the two major seasons in Ghana, and did not show variation in the composition and generation of waste. Similarly, studies on household waste quantity and composition by Anomanyo (2004), Dagadu (2005), Fobil et al. (2005) could not establish any seasonal trend. Hancs et al. (2011), postulates that seasonal variation normally affects generation of outdoor waste such as yard waste and the amount depends on the trimming rate. Table 2 below shows household waste compositions which support the fact that percentage organic waste contributes to majority of municipal solid waste in Ghana. Miezah et al. (2015), in similar findings, supports the fact that the high organic waste in Ghana's waste stream could be due to her dependency on agricultural products hence food waste formed the major sub fraction of organic waste analyzed.

Table 2; Household waste compositions in Ghana

Percentage fraction of household waste	Greater Accra (Newtown) (1)	Ashanti region (Asokwa (2)	Northern region (Tamale) (3)	Upper west region (Wa) (4)	Central region (cape coast) (5)	Western region (Tarkwa) (6)	Eastern region (Aburi) (7)
Organic	63	54.4	57.5	48	63	68.8	70
Paper	6	2.8	5	3	3	4.9	6
Plastic	10	6.8	20	5	2	16.0	16
Metal	2	1.7	10	5	1	2	3
Glass	2	1.1	5	-	1	0.9	5
Textile	5	1.8	-	4	1	3.23	-
Inert	12	31.4	2.5	33	26	4.2	-
Miscellaneous	3	4	-	2	3	0.3	-

(1) Owusu-Ansah (2008), (2) Asase (2011), (3) Puopiel (2010), (4) Monney et al. (2013), (5) Essumang (2000), (6) Ansah (2014) and (7) Asamoah-Okyere (2011), Miezah et al. (2015)

4.4 FRACTIONS OF MOST WASTED HOUSEHOLD FOOD

Percentage compositions of individual food waste among consumers in the three socio-economic class was determined, various factors which facilitated wastage among others includes; poor storage facilities, eruptive power supply, forgetfulness, purchasing too much proportion of foods, packaging, preparation methods, serving too much of the product and not interested in consuming the product anymore. The dairy products remained the predominant fraction in the household food waste followed by bread, vegetables and fruits as shown in figure 2 below. Dairy products consumed includes: cheese, yoghurt and fresh milk. High class income areas are aware of beneficial micronutrients from these products hence they attached much importance during purchasing which later generates wastage. Bakery product such as bread placed second as majority of households surveyed did not support the idea of refrigerator storing of bread as it loses its taste in the process. Fruits and vegetables classified as perishables will also find their way into the waste bins without proper storage facilities. Correlation between household income and residential status was not considered because some high income earners may choose to stay at lower income residential areas. Pichtel (2005) reported in his study that individuals in larger households generated less food waste compared to their counterparts in smaller households. This observation could be due to the fact that larger households always buy items in bigger packages which are shared by all members of the household which inherently limits amount of waste which could have been generated by single occupant in a household.

Fig 2; Percentage compositions of total household food waste analyzed.

Source; Researcher's field data (2016)

5.0 CONCLUSION

Knowledge about household food waste in Ghana is essential particularly when modern trend in agriculture production has changed over the years. Agriculture production recently is faced with many adverse environmental conditions, lack of proper land tenure system, land ownership constraints, lack of adequate subsidiaries, absence of modernized technologies and improper storage conditions. With the presence of these

inherent factors constraining productions and consumption in Ghana, the big question is “how can we still waste food whilst the country is heavily investing on importing food commodities” As stated earlier, Ghana in 2013 imported over 45% food commodities amounting over \$ 1.5 billion to compliment local production and demand, of which the country lost \$ 8.9 billion to both avoidable and unavoidable food wastage with the highest occurring with the distribution and consumer level of our food supply chain. Ghana, with a population of 24.4 million, generates 13,000 tons of waste daily, but lacks waste management infrastructure. The largest portion which is organic waste is from households located in high income class areas. In this present study, the high income class area generated 920.10 kg with highest food waste generation rate of 0.2 kg/person/day. Possible solutions such as proper freezing, measuring the right amount during preparation, checking expiry dates before purchasing, keeping food dairy, smart storage, buying the right amount and smart use of leftovers as recipes were selected as remedies to reducing instances of household food waste.

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